

Peculiarities of the Methodology of Working in Small Groups in the Process of Interactive Education

Dursunova Jamila Akhmatovna

Teacher, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

ABSTRACT

The article deals with analyzing peculiarities of the methodology of working in small groups in the process of interactive education. It is indicated that the implementation of the competency-based learning paradigm is possible using interactive methods. The model that promotes the formation of necessary competencies in the process of studying speech science disciplines, its main stages, implemented through various interactive techniques and teaching methods are briefly characterized. It is emphasized that the educational goal when working in a small group is achieved only through meaningful step-by-step implementation of a certain interactive teaching method.

Keywords: *small groups, interactive education, competency-based learning, educational goal, participants, collaboration.*

INTRODUCTION

Group work is one of our students' favorite forms of work. The most important thing for them is to overcome the fear of making mistakes and to feel more confident.

Working in small groups is one of the most popular interactive learning strategies, an integral part of many interactive methods, such as debates, training, creative tasks, public hearings, almost all types of games and simulations, litigation, etc.

Pair and group work is implemented both in the classroom system (lectures, practical and seminar classes), and in the conditions of independent training of students. This can happen immediately after the presentation of new material, at the beginning of the subsequent one, instead of a survey, during a practical lesson, or it can be part of a generalizing final lesson. This form is convenient because

students learn the material better, it helps develop their creative abilities, and, after all, the group form helps make the lesson more interesting. But the group form of work can also have a number of disadvantages.

Small group classes allow students to learn collaboration and other important interpersonal skills. In addition, these activities help students learn how to resolve disagreements between them. Study groups typically do not have many students who already have well-developed group skills. Therefore, such skills require careful training and long practice.

DISCUSSIONS

During a group project, students independently study the issues of the educational topic, solve practical problems or problems, or carry out some kind of project in order to prepare a defense for a group presentation (oral report, drawing, diagram, model, presentation).

The number of participants in a group can vary from 2-6 people. When working in groups, small groups are more effective because they are easier to organize, work faster, and give each student more opportunities to contribute to the work.

There are many ways to assign students to small groups. Here are just a few of them:

- It is possible to make a list of groups in advance and post them, indicating the meeting place of each group. In this case, you control the composition of the group.
- The simplest way of random distribution is to ask students to calculate “first or second...” according to the number of groups. After calculation, the first numbers form the first group, the second - the second, and so on. Instead of numbers, you can use colors, seasons, countries, etc.
- Another way is according to the position (or desire) of the students.

When working in a small group, students can perform the following roles:

- Facilitator (mediator-organizer of group activities);

- Recorder (records the results of work);
- Reporter (reports the results of the group's work to the whole class);
- Journalist (asks clarifying questions that help the group better complete the task, for example, questions that the other side in the discussion might ask);
- Active listener (trying to retell in his own words what one of the group members has just said, helping to formulate a thought);
- Observer (in addition, the observer can assign grades or points to each group member);
- Timekeeper (monitors the time allotted to complete the task).

Other roles are possible. The distribution of roles allows each group member to actively participate in the work. If the group remains stable for a long time, students should switch roles.

Teachers are encouraged to place excellent, average, and poor performing students in the same group. Diverse groups appear to experience greater creative thinking, more frequent sharing of explanations, and greater perspective-taking through discussion.

Some teachers do not change the composition of study groups throughout the entire program. It is helpful to maintain a stable group composition long enough for the group to be successful in its work. Disbanding underperforming groups is often counterproductive because students do not acquire the skills needed to solve problems together.

The study of interactive learning technologies is the next form of organizing cognitive mental activity. One of the many priority goals that it implements is the creation of comfortable learning conditions.

In the system of interactive work, the teacher plays the role of a participant in search activity, and not a leader who names his only correct way to solve a particular task. In interactive learning, the important thing is not how much children know, but how much they have learned and what they will do with their knowledge. The essence of interactive learning is that every student in the lesson is

placed in a situation of learning and cognition. Joint activity in such conditions contributes to the achievement of a common goal through the exchange of knowledge (information), ideas, methods of activity, etc. Comfortable conditions, an atmosphere of goodwill and mutual support are important in such work.

Creating an atmosphere of comfortable learning using interactive work methods contributes to the development of communication skills, the formation of a civic position, and promotes the establishment of emotional contacts. During lessons that are conducted in interaction mode, children can jointly express their thoughts, select evidence, exchange thoughts, and collectively find the right solution. In this work, they have psychological advantages, practice communication skills, are not afraid to make mistakes, and during training, relationships between students and teachers are built on trust.

The use of interactive technologies is not an end in itself. It is a way of creating an atmosphere that best promotes cooperation, understanding and goodwill, making it possible to truly realize student-centered learning. Interactive are special methods and mechanisms that provide continuous dialogue interactions between people.

The group planning stage can be carried out using planning sheets, where students write down the activity plan of each group member and their specific tasks.

At the research stage, semantic reading skills are well developed, students learn to use a variety of sources of information, when working with the test, they learn to select the necessary facts, make comparisons, establish a sequence, identify causes and consequences, and put forward hypotheses. For more successful learning of the material, it is best to use worksheet or route sheets.

An equally important process is the protection of research results, which is a type of collective activity.

A variety of group discussion are round table, discussion, dispute, debate.

The main features of the group (unit) form of organizing students' educational work:

- the class is divided into groups to solve specific educational problems;
- each group receives a specific task (either the same or differentiated) and performs it together under the direct guidance of a teacher or leader (speaker, group representative, headman, consultant) of the group;

During the work, group members are allowed to jointly discuss the progress and results of the work, and seek advice from each other.

The size of the groups varies. It ranges from 3-6 people. The optimal number of people, as experience shows, is 4-5 people, which allows you to "see" the work of each group member; in such a group it is more difficult to just sit out, because no one will carry out your task. The composition of the group changes depending on the content and nature of the work to be done.

The selection of the composition of the training group can be carried out taking into account:

- the level of schoolchildren's education, extracurricular awareness on this subject;
- the nature of student relationships, their compatibility (likes or dislikes), motives for interpersonal preferences, readiness to cooperate.
- There should be no students in the group who are negatively disposed towards each other.
- Group members must complement each other and compensate for deficiencies.

Group leader.

Leader selection, i.e. The responsibility for working in a group can be made by the teacher himself or, starting from the 7th grade, by the children themselves.

- Organization of training in small groups
- Training in small multi-level groups was carried out in several stages.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained, while simultaneously taking into account the wishes of the students, multi-level mobile groups were formed, i.e., involving a transition from group to group after conducting ongoing diagnostics of the effectiveness of group activities. Also, the diagnostic studies carried out helped the children decide on their roles (choose a captain, assistant captains, etc.)

Stage of modernization of the educational space. At this stage, it was decided that in lessons using group forms of work, the group on duty at recess would arrange desks in such a way that group members could freely interact face to face). Such joint activities stimulated their interest, while simultaneously preparing them for non-traditional forms of education.

Thus, working in small groups provides ample opportunities for self-control and mutual control. After all, it is in the group that reflection takes place, i.e. the ability to look at oneself from the outside, to evaluate one's contribution to the common cause. To do this, you can use self-assessment sheets and group activity analysis sheets. Group learning allows all students to actively participate in the learning process, be active, and collaborate with each other to achieve a positive result.

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